

STONE MONUMENT ENSEMBLES AND THE CLIMATE CHANGE IMPACT

Project ID: 101098422

DELIVERABLE 7.1

**DISSEMINATION, EXPLOITATION AND
COMMUNICATION PLAN**

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D7.1 – DISSEMINATION, COMMUNICATIONS AND EXPLOITATION PLAN

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Description of the related task and the deliverable

The present Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan, developed within Work Package WP7, will ensure that all required communication and dissemination from other WPs, as well as the utilization of STECCI project results, are coordinated. The document contains all the necessary information to facilitate the communication efforts of the STECCI project partners.

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SUMMARY

Once reviewed and approved by the Steering Committee, this document will become deliverable D7.1 - DISSEMINATION, EXPLOITATION AND COMMUNICATION PLAN of the STECCI project. Results and deliverables will be primarily carried out within the WP7, led by UNSPMF, contributed by COO UNSA. It will also include project activities from other work packages - WP3 and WP5 (Interdisciplinary workshops) and WP4 (Educational Game Development, Virtual Tours), WP5 and WP6 (workshops with multi stakeholders - onsite or hybrid). It outlines tools and strategies for dissemination and communication, serving as a guide for all project partners to achieve the greatest possible impact for the project. The objective of the Dissemination plan is to present the strategy for disseminating project progress and results to the public, relevant scientific communities, stakeholders, as well as raise awareness of its significance at the decision-making level. The scheduled dissemination actions can be assigned to

- internet-based communication
- publications in journals
- scientific conferences, workshops, social labs, training, and the summer academies
- cooperation with other projects

The Communication plan's goal is to present the communication actions, which will include several activities, to ensure the project's visibility and impact among the identified stakeholders. The communication plan specifies the target audience, channels, mechanisms, and activities that will be used to communicate the key messages of the project to various target groups.

It provides:

- description of the target audiences for communication actions
- communication content
- description of the main communication channels and activities
- scheduling and responsibilities of actions

Tailored Exploitation activities will be conducted to support the following objectives:

- exploitation of the project results
- validation of results
- awareness and endorsements by potential users
- commitments of partners for further STECCI results development.

The plan for Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation will be continuously monitored and revised, at least three times during the project's lifetime (reporting time), or more frequently if new target groups emerge or communication activities require revision. Promotional materials describing the Project's activities and outputs will be created and distributed at dissemination events and scientific conferences. Other forms of communication will include television broadcasts, press releases, and social networks. Each WP7 deliverable will be evaluated using the attendance list, evaluation form, event feedback summary form, and event report.

1. INTRODUCTION

Apart from DEC plan, the three others project pillars (the Project Management Plan, Quality Assurance Plan and Data Management Plan) are living documents that include agreed procedures within the Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Plan, which will be delivered at the start of the STECCI project and will be closely aligned with the other WPs activities, particularly the project strategy developed in WP7. The Plan will serve as the foundation for the project's dissemination and communication strategy, outlining the activities, channels, tools, and timing. Key stakeholders will be approached through a variety of dissemination and communication tools, distribution channels, and dedicated actions. It will use a targeted approach to relevant stakeholders and a dedicated multiplier program to generate local engagement and geographical balance. The development of a low-cost digitization methodology will support the EU policy mandating the 3D digitization of all endangered cultural heritage within the next few years.

The communication strategy will consider the different actions that will be implemented at local, regional, national, European, and global levels at varying intensities in order to generate a cascade effect on multiple targets and facilitate a variety of impacts, including consensus building, awareness, acceptance and replication.

This process will be boosted by a unified visual identity for all communication and dissemination efforts. In addition, the Plan will specify the internal consortium processes for the management of effective and efficient dissemination and communication activities at various geographical levels.

The Plan will be subject to updates and revisions to fine-tune the dissemination objectives as the project progresses, as well as to incorporate potential new targets, tools, channels, and communication strategies to be implemented throughout the project's duration.

2. STRATEGY FOR GENERAL COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION

One of the primary goals of communication and dissemination is to maximize the outreach: promote, communicate, and disseminate research findings throughout STECCI's lifetime and beyond. This ensures that key stakeholders can contribute to and act on the findings as soon as possible.

2.1 COMMUNICATION GOALS

The communication activities contribute to the achievement and preparation of project results, leading to validation of results, awareness, and endorsements by reaching multiple audiences: potential customers, citizens, the media, diverse group of stakeholders so as to trigger further exploitation plans, partner commitments for current and future development, and, eventually, market uptake. The impact will be communicated outside of the consortium.

The STECCI communication objectives align with the recommendations of the European Commission (EC) for communicating EU research and innovation. The project will disseminate information about the action and its results to a variety of audiences, including the media and the broader public.

2.2 DISSEMINATION OBJECTIVES

The scientific dissemination activities include publishing and presenting scientific results in international and domestic conferences and journals, scientific magazines and other scientific oriented activities and events. Foreseen dissemination channels also include internet-based communication instruments, such as websites, social media accounts and digital newsletters, that reaches the wide audience from stakeholders and research institutes to public.

The dissemination activities are in line with the EU Open Science and support objectives set to achieve and prepare exploitation of the project results and lead to validation of results, awareness and endorsements by potential users, exploitation plans, commitments of partners for further development and market uptake. Dissemination is aimed at the community of peers but not limited to them. Other stakeholders should also learn from the results: authorities, industry, policymakers, sectors of interest, civil society. In this way the impact can be spread outside the consortium and gain market for partners on a larger scale.

2.3 EXPLOITATION STRATEGIES

Exploitation strategies are about making concrete use of the project results and will capitalize knowledge and technology developed throughout the lifespan of the project to bring value generated to the market and society, from an educational, scientific, political, and societal perspective. This deliverable aims to present STECCI key exploitable results and to identify potential fields for exploitation beyond the end of the project. The methodology is based on a stepwise approach: preliminary identification by the consortium of expected exploitable results; assessment of the innovation and market potential of key exploitable results (identification of those with a high potential) and creating tailor-made business models built in accordance with the nature of the result and the profile of the owner.

The visibility of some key emerging technologies through new products and services will be demonstrated to encourage community uptake, and progress tracking indicators beyond the project's duration. STECCI's efforts and findings will be summarized and disseminated at the final inter-disciplinary STECCI Conference.

3. DEC CHANNELS

This section will introduce the main tools that will be used to share project information. External communication channels include the following:

- STECCI Promo film
- Project website and Platform
- International repositiorium (both Mendeley and Sketchfab)
- Conference publications
- Scientific papers in Open Access peer reviewed journals
- Press releases

- Newsletter
- Social Media
- Events
- Promotional material
- Media reports

3.1 COMMUNICATION CHANNELS STRATEGY

This section of the communications strategy provides best practice tips and examples for expanding the reach and impact of STECCI communications activities. When selecting the appropriate channel, it is critical to address the right message to the right audience via the appropriate channel.

3.1.1 THE MESSAGE'S CONTENT

The best way to share will be determined by the composition of the content. Text-heavy content is best suited for the website, whereas only visual content will have a greater impact on social media.

3.1.2 AUDIENCE FOCUSING

Different target audiences will respond to various communication channels: youth via social media, press via mailings, and members via the website and newsletters. Understanding the preferences of an audience can enhance the effectiveness of communications.

3.1.3 THE JUSTIFICATION FOR SHARING

The purpose of the post is crucial: a post intended to engage directly with recipients is better suited for social media, whereas sharing important information that must be stored permanently is better suited for the website. Due to the variety of Project activities and data formats, STECCI will be promoted through several professional channels.

3.1.4 APPROPRIATE TIMING

"Tweets," for example, have a half-life of 25 minutes and receive 75% of engagement within 3 hours. The best times for social media are 14h, 17h, and 18h. Newsletters are most effective at 09.30h or 14h. The frequency with which information is shared is critical: multiple tweets per day, and e.g. one or two articles per week. Posting at the appropriate frequency will maximize the effectiveness of each tool.

3.1.5 PROJECT WEBSITE AND PLATFORM

The project website is an important communication tool for increasing project visibility and impact, especially among larger communities and the public. All relevant project information will be available on the STECCI website, which is available online and updated on a regular basis - project objectives, information, news, event announcements, public reports, analysis etc.

The website for the project was launched before the scheduled M2 <https://steccihorizoneu.com/>

The website is fulfilling one level of communication: external communication. It will be used as a platform to inform about the status, upcoming events, and deadlines. The website will be maintained for at least five years after the project ends. A general project website provides information on the project, project partners, and research activities and outcomes. To normalize engineering roles for women, all information on the website will be gender neutral.

The homepage is updated regularly with the newest information related to the project. The website contains a “News and events” section where all new developments within the project would be documented as news pieces. They are then visible to all project members and external website visitors.

The website will be updated on a regular basis as the project progresses. It will announce upcoming project-related events and will be the environment in which all relevant publishable documents generated by the consortium will be uploaded to make them available to the public. The interface is user-friendly. It is routinely updated with information about the ongoing and future STECCI activities/events, DEC networks between beneficiaries as well as various target groups (universities and schools, regional and trans-regional policy makers, representatives from networks of sustainable cultural heritage, representatives from wider tourism industry etc.).

STECI external Platform - the platform will have two focus points: a) Workshops and Social Labs promotion and b) Summer academies promotion. It will contain all the STECCI related material in an interactive mode with remote access to the specific topics available without registration. Also, it will enable users to: connect and collaborate; search professionals in a particular field; create project proposals effectively; share publications and results; ask questions, get answers, and solve research issues; share updates about current projects; keep up with the latest news and research in the field.

3.1.6 CONFERENCE PUBLICATIONS

To disseminate research results with an eye toward STECCI's long-term impact, the project will also target key relevant scientific journals. Publication in peer-reviewed journals will lend legitimacy to the project results, as well as encourage external stakeholders to participate in the project and possibly increase STECCI results adoption. For this reason, all publications will be open access to facilitate access (to the extent possible).

3.1.7 SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL

Using an open-access publishing model, at least five original research articles will be submitted to peer-reviewed scientific journals with Impact Factor of >2. Additional papers may be published in Open Research Europe (ORE), at no cost, and in full compliance with EU open access policies. Open access to all scientific publications resulting from STECCI will be promoted in accordance with Regulation (EU) No 1290/2013, as well as the national regulators bodies. All papers derived from the STECCI project will acknowledge the European Commission for project funding.

It was agreed that the following plan will be followed:

1st project year – at least one paper submission from WP2

2nd project year - at least one submission form WP3

3rd project year – at least one paper submission from WP5 and WP6

3.1.8 MEDIA AND PRESS-RELEASE

Media and press-release (TV broadcasts, online news portals, newspapers) – will be used as an effective channel to communicate, promote, and inform the public about the STECCI project and the Horizon Europe funding program.

The first Promo video was released by M1.

There will be two methods for distributing press releases: top-down and bottom-up.

When major project news, such as policy recommendations or significant project results, must be disseminated to a wider audience, a press release will be written and distributed to major European news organizations such as Reuters and other pan-European news agencies, after consulting and approving by PO. Partners will also share the information with their own regional, national, or even local media contacts, depending on its relevance. Bottom-up press releases will begin on a smaller scale, either locally or regionally, and will then be disseminated on a national or even European scale. These press releases are used to publicize localized events, project results, and other information that is not relevant to a broader international audience. Additionally, all press releases will be posted online. Regular press releases will be issued at the European and national levels to coincide with significant project events and milestones.

3.1.9 MANAGEMENT OF THE PRESS RELEASE

UNSPMF and UNSA will coordinate the formation of a communication working group (CWG) consisting of one representative from each consortium member. This CWG will meet regularly to assess and enhance the communication strategy. The UNSPMF will provide an intranet tool or platform containing all necessary documents, such as general guidelines, visual identity elements (logos and disclaimers) to be used in communication tasks and corresponding templates, and tools to ensure adequate external communication. The press release template will be accessible in the "STECCI Templates" section of the platform.

3.1.10 NEWSLETTERS AND EMAIL

Email will be one of the credible means of STECCI's stakeholder outreach to inform interested parties about events and activities. Emails will allow partners to conduct small-scale, targeted outreach with a more personal feel that is as flexible as possible and requires no central coordination; however, while e-mail is a simple form of communication, it can be difficult to plan and measure its effectiveness strategically. Information on STECCI research and adaptation in Europe will be disseminated to a broader audience via newsletters and/or thematic fact sheets. The newsletter will be emailed via the web-based platform, with a direct link to the website's content. The use of an email newsletter permits the collection of more comprehensive monitoring and evaluation data.

3.2 SOCIAL MEDIA NETWORKS

Twitter, Instagram, YouTube, FB and LinkedIn (instead of Tik-Tok, as agreed on KoM)

Hashtags: #EUCommission, #HE, #STECCI_EU and Tag: @european-commission and

Also: @EU_STECCI must then be added to each post that is not placed on the STECCI page.

Facebook (Note: In October 2021, Facebook Inc. announced that it would change its company name to Meta Platforms Inc. or "Meta" to reflect its focus on building the "metaverse," a digital universe. Despite this, the Facebook app and website retain their original name)

Facebook users can publish text, images, and video content that can be viewed and shared with other users who have consented to be their friends or, depending on the privacy settings, made public. Messenger enables users to engage in direct notifications regarding the whereabouts of Facebook friends and the pages they follow.

Twitter (X)

In Twitter, users can post and interact with messages publicly, though you can also send private "Direct" messages. Users can "follow" other accounts to create a personalized feed of tweets from these accounts on their own Twitter timeline. You can like, share (retweet), comment (reply), or save those tweets to refer back later. Adding hashtags (#) to the tweet topic or category makes it easier for others to find tweets on a particular topic. Twitter is known for its real-time updates, making it a source for users to stay updated on news, events, and topics that interest them

LinkedIn

After carefully analysing a variety of social media platforms, it was anticipated that LinkedIn will emerge as a top-performer with many experts, businesses and stakeholders from the Projects field active across this media. As we strive to connect with a wide range of professionals and foster meaningful collaborations, LinkedIn offers the ideal environment for these interactions.

Instagram

An Instagram page has been created for the project to reach the general public and in particular, the younger, more visually oriented people. Instagram's emphasis on visual storytelling and its powerful editing tools have attracted a huge user base, helping it grow rapidly since its inception. Today, Instagram is one of the largest global social networks, boasting more than 1 billion active monthly users.

YouTube

A YouTube account has been created to serve the purpose of a video repository and host all the project videos. This platform also enables the videos' integration with other communication channels, further empowering our communication and dissemination strategy. A YouTube channel is like a personal space or profile for a user or a business on YouTube, where users can post, host, and share videos, interact with subscribers and viewers, and manage content.

Tik Tok

In addition to creating content, the algorithm of the app helps users discover new content and creators, making it an effective platform for viral trends. TikTok has gained enormous popularity, especially among Gen Z users, with over 1 billion active users worldwide as of 2021.

Project newsletter

The STECCI Communication Team has created a Newsletter account, which will allow us to send our newsletters during key times of the project and disseminate project updates, community news, and upcoming events. We will use email marketing to foster engagement with our audience, as well as inform, thus creating value for our readers. The newsletter will be issued quarterly, and readers can subscribe to it through the projects' website.

3.3 PARTNER RESPONSIBILITIES

Main points of the action plan:

- The communication activities are led by UNSPMF, with a strong contribution from COO and ALL Partners
- The WP Leaders have the responsibility of contributing to the creation of content related to their WP activities, to be communicated in the various channels.
- All partners play a crucial role in communicating the project at a local, national, and European level.
- The communication tools and channels, as well as the promotional materials planned, support the STECCI consortium in reaching out to the target stakeholders with the maximum impact.

Table 1. DEC plan

Target	Communication type	Purpose	Scheduling
Representatives of all partners and WP7 Leader	Kick-off meeting	Sharing practical information and familiarization of consortium members. Selected CWG members.	September 2023
Communication Working Group	Face-to- face online meetings	Strategic decisions regarding the project direction and responsibilities of consortium members	At least once a month
All consortium members	Consortium meeting in teleconference or face-to-face	Information exchange and networking within consortium, addressing of cross-WP technical issues	On demand
COO and WP leaders	Teleconference or face-to-face	Decisions on executive matters	On demand
EC representative	Review meetings	Review the results of the reporting period	Once in every reporting period. Three times in total.
COO, WP and task leaders, project key persons	Working meetings, mainly teleconference	Discussions about detailed issues in WPs	On demand
Events DEC	Workshops, Summer academies (Trainings, Social labs etc) Scientific conferences	Gathering feedback and ideas from field personnel. Introduction to new applications and training	Task 3.5 Interdisciplinary Workshop (25-27M) Task 5.2 At least two in Germany STECCI Lab to life (8-21M) Task 5.2 CS workshop Serbia (8-21M) Task 3.6 and Task 5.3 Summer academies (three, in M22, M35, M37) Task 7.6 Scientific conference 24-27M Vienna Task 7.6 Scientific conference 43-48 Mdina 2027

3.4 VISUAL IDENTITY OF THE PROJECT

An easily recognizable (visual) identity of the project is essential to achieve best communication results. A Visual Identity Guide will be created by WP7 Leader UNSPMF and made available to project partners to apply during communication and dissemination activities. It is of high importance to use these visual tools coherently. All logos will be available on the internal collaboration platform on STECCI document portal, as high-resolution image files.

3.4.1 VISUAL TOOLS:

Project logo (in English)

Templates (ppt, project newsletter, press release, scientific conference presentation, policy brief, paper, HE reporting/deliverable, etc.)

General flyer/project brochure (in English)

Project poster (in English)

General project website (in English)

Grant Agreement number – partners are requested to use the project GA number in all of the external communication and dissemination materials.

DEC activities must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate):

https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/information-sources/logo-download-center_en

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LOGO Brand definition (by M2)

3.4.2 ABBREVIATION STECCI

Using the acronym alone without the *symbol* or *Logo* is not allowed, as this would significantly compromise the integrity of the brand.

Symbol with STECCI acronym (for social media)

Partners are required to use the logos, colours of the visual identity and the STECCI templates. The STECCI LOGO consists of several graphic elements, which at the same time form a brand.

3.4.3 LOGO PROTECTION ZONE AND COLOR SCHEME

The logo's protection zone is its sovereign space, which must not be compromised by other graphic elements, images, or text. The logo is shielded from the negative effects of other graphic elements by a protection zone, ensuring a positive brand perception and legibility.

When displayed in association with other logos (e.g., STECCI Project logo or of the beneficiaries), the emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos.

3.4.4 QUALITY OF INFORMATION — DISCLAIMER

Any communication or dissemination activity related to the action must use factually accurate information. Moreover, it must indicate the following disclaimer (translated into local languages where appropriate):

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or [name of the granting authority]. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

3.4.5 SPECIFIC COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION, AND VISIBILITY RULES

Literature should be cited using the Chicago (or APA alternatively) style.

For the in-text citation, both formats contain the author's last name and a page number in parentheses. The year of publication of the source is also included in APA Style, but not in Chicago (Turabian) Style. To cite your sources, Chicago (Turabian) Style allows you to use footnotes rather than in-text citations.

The steps below should be used to change the style of a works cited list or bibliography.:

1. On the View menu, click Draft or Print Layout.
2. On the References tab, click Citations.
3. In the Citations pane, on the Citation style list, select a style. All references in your document's bibliography change to the new style.

3.4.6. PROJECT REFERENCE

General

This project has received funding from the European Union's HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions under Grant Agreement No 101094822 (STECCI)

Scientific papers acknowledgment

'This research has been supported by the Horizon Research and Innovation Actions under Grant Agreement No 101094822 (STECCI)'

DOCUMENTS IDs

Emails STECCI + event/activity

Documents YYMMDD_STECCI_name of document

Deliverables Deliverable.No_STECCI_deliverable short name

Other specific communication, dissemination, and visibility rules are set out in STECCI Branding rules given in Appendix 5.

4. DISSEMINATION PLAN

4.1 DISSEMINATION OF KNOWLEDGE WITHIN THE STECCI CONSORTIUM

Dissemination also includes communication within the consortium and methods of communicating results between partners. All data and information will be stored using an online data management tool to which all partners have access. Standard methods of sharing information include:

- Regular reviews at WP, task, and project levels.
- Use of web-conferencing between partner institutions.
- Training and research exchange from within the consortium.
- Knowledge-sharing visits between partner institutions.

Links will be established with other projects working in this area (via project partners, platforms such as NECROPOLA, and Open Research Europe) for greater transparency, higher citation rates, views, downloads, media attention, opportunities for collaboration and visibility.

To establish a link early in the project, STECCI will also invite representatives from European and national regulatory bodies to the annual consortium meetings. This will facilitate the uptake of STECCI results in regulations and policies.

4.1.1 USING EMDESK FOR DISSEMINATION OF KNOWLEDGE WITHIN THE STECCI CONSORTIUM

EMDESK is a single, flexible project and financial management platform that unifies planning, controlling, execution, and collaboration in projects. It helps teams and stakeholders to work together, while maintaining maximum control and transparency. EMDESK offers effective instruments for monitoring project progress and consumption against timelines and budget forecasts, while collecting and consolidating reporting data efficiently, with collated status overviews of the projects (spreadsheets, Kanban boards, and Gantt charts) for performance and financial activity by teams and reporting periods – all the way down to the task level. EMDESK will allow everyone to track progress and consumption in real time with effortless reporting features and free up time to focus on the actual work, providing regular status updates and gain valuable insight with progress and financial reports, integrating collaboration, linking information to project objectives, and improving result quality.

EMDESK optimizes flow of information, eliminates redundant email exchange and increases productivity. With intuitive work management and communication features, we will be able to collaborate, share, and have discussions efficiently. It maximizes content value and accelerates information flow with contextualized documents related to the project activities and tasks. It also enables instant access and speedy retrieval through search, indexing, categorization, tagging, and ratings, sharing folders or documents internally but also to externals easily, without giving them project access.

The EMDESK platform performers to:

- Provide financial and administrative management in addition to ensuring the effective coordination and administration of all technical and administrative aspects.
- Ensures and supports the exchange of information and communication between the Steering Committee, the PO, and the consortium partners.
- Guarantees optimal reporting implementation and integration, as well as progress reports of the highest quality.
- Guarantees data management guiding principles (including the FAIR principle, data security, and ethical considerations); permits monitoring of the project's impact.

The EMDESK internal communication strategy was developed to achieve the following objectives:

1. To ensure that every member of the project is informed about the ongoing activities of the project and the specific outcomes that will be achieved.
2. Foster a collective commitment among all project participants to actively participate in order to ensure the effective tasks execution.
3. To oversee the expectations of all project participants. The coordinator and the partners want to establish a reputation as a reliable source of creative and high-quality information.
4. Disseminate precise and timely information to all participants of the project regarding the forthcoming procedures. This will facilitate the execution of the project, therefore ensuring the achievement of the project's goals (APPENDIX 6)

4.2 DISSEMINATION TO TARGET AUDIENCE

The development of the Stakeholder Database commences during the early months of the project and remains an ongoing activity throughout its full extent. Throughout the entirety of the project, all stakeholder data and interactions will be primarily referenced from the STECCI database.

The STECCI Stakeholder Database is established in accordance with the relevant procedures and guidelines:

- a. A MS Office.xls file is developed including the pre-defined categories and criteria for mapping.
- b. All consortium partners were requested to enter the information about the potential stakeholders in this template spreadsheet (still pending request).

The information collected in this database will include:

- i. Personal information about stakeholders: name, affiliation, position in the organization, contact information (only if this is publicly available),
- ii. Name, acronym, website, sector, geographical focus, level, and type of organization. These categories will aid in the creation of a unified stakeholder mapping.
- iii. Additional mapping criteria and categories will be developed in close collaboration with the project team and in response to the requirements of the work packages.

The data collection process will comply with the principles and standards outlined in the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Contact information will be withheld from this database unless it is publicly accessible, or the stakeholder has explicitly consented to sharing it for project-related purposes.

The information contained in the STECCI Stakeholder Database would not be posted online (i.e., it shall not be exposed to third parties nor linked to any commercial purpose); rather, it shall serve exclusively to ensure stakeholder engagement for the project. The process of identifying and mapping potential stakeholders is continuous. All project-related information will be consistently updated in the stakeholder database. It is requested that partners update the records whenever a new candidate is discovered.

For partners, a manual with instructions on how to use the database and map stakeholders is prepared.

The following target audiences of STECCI results have been defined:

- Civil Society: conservators, artists and cultural/creative workers, NGOs, youth organizations, education institutes, public, media groups.
- Industry: Private sector (tourism, farmers, business associations), Public Sector: Tourism, Spatial Planning.
- Academia: scientific community; students, NEKROPOLA platform, European structures supporting research and innovation (Horizon Europe), European and International Initiatives (IPCC).
- Government: Stakeholders, Policymakers from local and regional authorities, Policy implementers at European and national agencies, Policy makers from the European Commission Groups Communication tools and channels.

The project will use a variety of educational activities to create a platform for better knowledge, experience, and collaboration among local communities, academia, stakeholders, and decision makers. Summer Academies dedicated to conservation work, citizen science, and cultural tourism with creative workshops, hands-on training for young researchers and conservators, art exhibitions, open dialogue sessions, and conferences will be among the activities. A critical goal is the transfer of knowledge and skills among beneficiaries, who will share the novel and holistic science-based approach to conservation via open-access sources. The goal is primarily measurable through the completion of three summer academies and cultural heritage festivals held in different countries (B&H, HR, MNE), as well as two scientific conferences and other forms of education. Using the STECCI Platform, a variety of target groups, including universities and schools, regional and trans-regional policy makers, representatives from networks of sustainable cultural heritage, representatives from the broader tourism industry, and social, eco, and creative entrepreneurs, will collaborate.

4.3 PUBLICATION PRINCIPLES

4.3.1 BASIC PRINCIPLES

The dissemination practices and publication procedures to be followed are described in Article 15 and Article 17 of the Grant Agreement.

4.3.2 OPEN ACCESS PUBLISHING IN HE

Open access shall be ensured (Details given in GA).

Each beneficiary must ensure open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to their results by:

- Self-archiving (also known as "green" open access). Before, alongside, or after publication, a published article or the final peer-reviewed manuscript is archived (deposited) in an online repository. Beneficiaries must ensure open access to the publication within a maximum of six months if this route is chosen (twelve months for publications in social sciences and humanities).
- Open access publishing (including 'gold' open access, in which an article is immediately made open access on the publisher/journal website). At the same time, a copy should be deposited in a repository.

5. DMP RELATED TO DISSEMINATION, COMMUNICATION AND EXPLOITATION PLAN

5.1 STRATEGY FOR THE MANAGEMENT OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY

The Lead Partner will be responsible for IP management, together with WP7 leading beneficiary. STECCI will generate a range of R&D results, documents, publications, and outputs such as data, tools and knowledge, collated in a platform, according to STECCI Data Management Plan (DMP). STECCI's outputs will adhere to open science principles and the consortium will ensure that any knowledge generated through this project is managed and appropriately protected consistent with the EU Intellectual Property Action Plan [COM (2020) 760 final]. Management of data and knowledge will be in accordance with the Commission's contractual rules and will follow the DESCA 2020 model Consortium agreement (CA). The major principle in the CA for management of knowledge, signed by all partners, is that knowledge developed under STECCI (IPR, data etc.) should be open and available for all project partners

5.2 DATA PROCESSING BY THE GRANTING AUTHORITY

Any personal data under the Agreement will be processed under the responsibility of the data controller of the granting authority in accordance with and for the purposes set out in the Portal Privacy Statement as well as STECCI DMP, the processing will be subject to Regulation 2018/1725¹.

¹ Regulation (EU) 2018/1725 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2018 on the protection of natural persons regarding the processing of personal data by the Union institutions, bodies, offices and agencies and on the free movement of such data and repealing Regulation (EC) No 45/2001 and Decision No 1247/2002/EC (OJ L 295, 21.11.2018, p. 39).

6. EXPLOITATION

STECCI exploitation plan will include 1) an attractive knowledge portfolio to continue enhancing the innovations after the project end; 2) a description of the steps to promote Heritage conservation on Online Platform.

The methodology is based on a step-wise approach: i) preliminary identification by the consortium of expected exploitable results; ii) assessment of the innovation and market potential of key exploitable results (identification of those with a high potential); iii) creating tailor-made business models built in accordance with the nature of the result and the profile of the owner; iv) prioritization of the main applicable standards in the sector; v) generating joint and individual exploitation plans. The visibility of some key emerging technologies through new products and services will be demonstrated to encourage community uptake, and progress tracking indicators beyond the project's duration. STECCI's efforts and findings will be summarized and disseminated at the final inter-disciplinary STECCI Conference. Adoption of the deliverables by as many Stakeholders and government agencies as possible will be a crucial success factor for STECCI, ultimately resulting in the development of the Preservation Guidelines, STECCI Handbook and Policy Brief for sustainable STECCI-specific management and tourism.

7. DEC MEASURES

7.1 COMMUNICATION MEASURES AND INDICATORS

To assess our strategy's reach and impact on various target groups, qualitative and quantitative performance indicators will be developed. These indicators will be linked to the project's objectives and will allow us to assess the effectiveness of our communication strategies.

Quantitative indicators include, for example, the number of communication actions, the number of newsletters and press releases, the number of publications edited, the number of website visits, the number of social media users, and the number of people attending communication events. The qualitative indicators reflect the quality of the interaction with the population based on online questionnaires to website visitors, questionnaires to communication event participants, and feedback from the public and specific target groups.

Table 2. KPIs of communication measures

Method/Channel	KPI	Target	Contingency
STECCI website	Site visits (per month)	min. 20	Consortium members will promote the website at their respective institutions and WP7 via social networks.
	Countries that accessed the site (per year)	min 10	STECCI and other conferences, summer academies, scientific publications will all contribute to an international interest in the project website.
Social networks	Responds (per month)	Min 30	Young people will be asked to share their knowledge, opinions and ideas on topics related to CC and heritage.
	Active followers on Meta per year	Min 100	Active followers will be recruited through posts linked to trending hashtags.
Summaries of STECCI on the partner official sites	During and after the project	Min 7	STECCI consortium consists of 9 partners and min 9 will post summaries of STECCI on their official internet sites.
Press releases	Published (in four years)	40	The STECCI project promotion will take place in all 8 partner countries. Lead members of partners will plan the press releases in cooperation with WP7.
Kinds of distributed promo materials	No of different kinds of promo materials (yearly)	4	Different events will ask for different types of promo materials.
Video materials on STECCI website and social networks	Broadcast rating and number of views (by the end of the project)	Min 50 views	WP7 in cooperation with WP5 will prepare the video materials and promote them during the project's events.
Each partner's website	Posts of events (during project duration)	Min 2	Each partner will create posts of events that are most related to their WP and/or tasks.

Table 3. KPIs of dissemination and exploitation measures

Method/Channel	KPI	Target	Contingency
Workshops	Participants (per workshop)	Min 15	Website, promo materials, social network posts will be designed for specific target groups to attract their interest
Hands-on training for students of conservation	Student participants (per academy)	15-20	Partner institutions (universities) will promote the project activity and directly involve their students
European days of cultural heritage	Participants (per event)	Min 80	WP7 will actively work on the promotion and organisation of the event
Interdisciplinary workshop on the enhanced application of analytical methods in conservation science	Participants (per workshop)	20-30	WP1 and WP3 will prepare the event's agenda and highlight the benefits for participants
Festivals	Participants (per festival)	Min 80	Target groups actively involved in social labs will represent the network of potential participants. The festivals will be promoted via the website, promo materials, social networks, TV broadcasts
Scientific conferences	Number of participants (per conference)	Min 80	UNSPMF (lead of WP7) in cooperation with other partner institutions will prepare the agenda, which will be reviewed and approved by the Steering Committee and Advisory Board to maximise the effects and quality of the conferences. The events will be promoted via STECCI website, partners' official websites, media releases, sent out invitations.
Hands-on training, European days of cultural heritage, Interdisciplinary workshop on the enhanced application of analytical methods in conservation science, Scientific conferences	Summary of participants' feedback (grade)	Percentage of quality ratings (scale 1-5, min 1, max 5) received by min 55% of participants. The event received an overall rating of over 3.	To increase the quality, direct benefits and impacts of the organised events the programmes will be carefully tailored to specific target groups by WP leaders and approved by the Steering committee.

8. EVALUATION OF DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION EVENTS

Indicators of successful event dissemination will be evaluated using the Attendance List (Appendix 1), the Participant Feedback Form (Appendix 2), the Participant Feedback Summary Form (Appendix 3, to be filled by host institution), and the Event Report (Appendix 4, to be filled by host institution).

9. GENDER EQUALITY

Equal treatment between the genders is a core principle of the European Union (https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/democracy-and-rights/gender-equality-research-and-innovation_en#gender-equality-plans-as-an-eligibility-criterion-in-horizon-europe) By increasing the quality and relevance of research and innovation (R&I), recruiting, and retaining more talent, and guaranteeing that all individuals may reach their full potential, gender equality is advantageous to R&I. Despite apparent advancements in gender equality within the European Research Area (ERA), empirical evidence indicates that substantial efforts remain. The objective of implementing the Gender Equality Plan (GEP) eligibility criterion is to help with these activities, along with the legal framework of Horizon Europe that prioritises gender equality across all domains. As of calls for proposals with deadlines beginning in 2022, the following categories of legal entities incorporated in EU Member States or Associated countries are mandatory to have a GEP for individual organizations applying to any share of Horizon Europe: Public entities, including research funding bodies, national ministries, and other public authorities, including for-profit organizations); Public and private higher education institutions; Public and private research organizations.

Regarding research organizations and institutions, the European Commission defines a Gender Equality Plan as a series of measures that aim to achieve the following objectives:

- Identify and implement innovative strategies to rectify any gender bias that may be present; • Establish targets and monitor progress through the use of indicators; and
- Conduct impact assessments and audits of procedures and practices to identify gender bias.

The purpose of a GEP is to advance gender equality within an organization by means of institutional and cultural transformation. It consists of a series of commitments and actions. When developing a GEP there are some essential elements – ‘building blocks’ – which must be included.

To comply with the HE GEP eligibility criterion, a GEP must meet four mandatory process-related requirements:

1. Formal document: The GEP should be a publicly available document that is formally published on the organization's website, bearing the signature of the highest-ranking executive, and proactively disseminated among all members of the institution. It must exhibit a steadfast dedication to promoting gender equality by establishing unambiguous objectives accompanied by comprehensive strategies and implementation plans to attain them.

2. Dedicated resources: A GEP must have the resources and knowledge necessary to implement the plan about gender equality. It is imperative for organizations to deliberate on the nature and quantity of resources necessary to sustain a continuous process of organizational change.

3. Data collection and monitoring: organizations must collect sex/ gender disaggregated data on personnel (and students, for the establishments concerned) with annual reporting based on indicators.
4. Training: The GEP must also include awareness-raising and training actions on gender equality. These activities should engage the whole organisation and be an evidence-based, ongoing and long-term process.

All the STECCI partner institutions had already submitted a self-declaration at the GA preparation stage, through a specific questionnaire confirming they have a GEP in place. This declaration will later be included in the entity validation process. If the four mandatory requirements are met through another strategic document, such as an inclusion or diversity strategy, it will be considered as a GEP equivalent.

9.1 PRESENT STECCI GE DATA

At this moment, data collection about the gender diversity of people involved in experimental laboratory activities is in its initial stage. However, this aspect will be constantly monitored and analysed in the DEC update edition. The gender distribution at the management level of the STECCI consortium is exceptionally equitable (coordinator, project manager, and eight partner coordinators collectively represent a literal 50:50 ratio), with over fifty percent of high-performing WP leaders, co-leaders, and task leaders being female. In recent times, there has been a growing recognition of the need to address gender bias and disparities in conjunction with other forms of inequality, including but not limited to disability, age, sexual orientation, religion, and ethnicity. By addressing additional inequities that overlap with gender, effective mechanisms for change may be created, and complete actions and strategies may be inspired. In light of this, a thorough gender and ethics plan will be prepared in advance for the subsequent stages of project implementation in line with ethics requirements and Quality Assurance Plan.

10. CONCLUSION

This document presents the consortium strategy for the dissemination, communication and exploitation for STECCI. It identifies the projects objectives, tools, channels and overall strategies to efficiently communicate, disseminate and exploit towards the projects objectives and intended outputs. This Plan will be updated and followed by a related deliverable, namely D7.5 and D7.7. (Dissemination and Exploitation Report updates, M36, M48).

11. REFERENCES

Grant Agreement 101094822— STECCI

https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-08/imcap-article-17-eu-visibility_en.pdf

[/rea.ec.europa.eu/dissemination-and-exploitation](https://rea.ec.europa.eu/dissemination-and-exploitation)

<file:///C:/Users/Korisnik/Downloads/horizon%20europe%20guidance%20on%20gender%20equality%20plans-KI0221806ENN.pdf>

APPENDIX 1. ATTENDANCE LIST

Event title Title

Work package WP Number

Task Task Number

Event date dd/mm/yy - dd/mm/yy

Venue Place

Event organizer Name partner

No	Name and surname	Affiliation	E-mail	Signature
1				
2				
3				
4				
5				
6				
7				
8				
9				

APPENDIX 2. PARTICIPANT FEEDBACK FORM - MEETING/WORKSHOP/ SUMMER ACADEMIA/ TRAINING /CONFERENCE (TO BE FILLED BY PARTICIPANTS)

Event Information

Event Title

Date (dd/mm/yy)

Venue

Work Package

Task

Host institution

Period of event assessed (please, mark one of options): entirely / partly.

Overall assessment (descriptive please)

Participant's name

_____ Signature _____

Event organization and structure					
Organizational feature	5 Strongly agree	4 Agree	3 Neither agree nor disagree	2 Disagree	1 Strongly disagree
The objectives of the event were clearly defined					
Information related to each item prepared well in advance of the event					
The material distributed were helpful and on time					
The presentations met my expectation					
Participation and interactions were encouraged by moderator					
The event objectives were met					
I will be able to apply the event's content in my future work					
The event content was challenging enough					
The timeframe was adequate					
The facilities were adequate					
Skill practice sessions were included					
Suggestion and criticism box (please specify)					

APPENDIX 3. ORGANIZERS FEEDBACK SUMMARY - MEETING/WORKSHOP/SUMMER ACADEMIA/TRAINING/ CONFERENCE

Work package	WP Number
Task	Task Number
Event title	Title
Event date	dd/mm/yy - dd/mm/yy
Venue	Place
Type of event	Live / Online / Hybrid
Event organizer	Name partner
Authors	Name Surname (Partner Y)
Reviewers	Name Surname (Partner Y)

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

PURPOSE, OBJECTIVES AND ELEMENTS OF EVENT

LIST OF PARTICIPANTS AND AFFILIATIONS

CONCLUSIONS

EVENT PHOTOS

WEBLINKS TO MEDIA RELEASES

APPENDIX 4. TEMPLATES

This Appendix comprises a collection of documents developed and required for the project's first phase. All of the templates can be accessed on the STECCI EMDESK platform / WP7 Documents.

<https://stecci.emdesk.com/#!/documents/all/>

E-MAIL SIGNATURE TEMPLATE

Based on the STECCI logo, three versions of the email signature were created.

Snezana Radulovic

WP7 UNSPMF

STECCI

[+387XXXXXXXXXX](tel:+387XXXXXXXXXX)

snezana.radulovic@dbe.uns.ac.rs

<https://steccihorizoneu.com/>

Trg Dositeja Obradovića 2, Novi Sad

EVENT INVITATION TEMPLATE

Canva and PPT were used to create an invitation to the STECCI project presentation and events.

Slide 4 (right): A detailed event invitation slide. The header is dark blue with the STECCI logo, the text 'STECCI Invitation', a calendar icon, the date '22 September 2023', and the URL 'steccihorizoneu.com'. The main content area is light blue and contains the following sections:

- PRESENTATION OF HORIZON EUROPE PROJECT OPPORTUNITIES**
- STECCI AS WORLD HERITAGE**
- PRESENTATION OF THE HORIZON EUROPE PROJECT STONE MONUMENT ENSAMBLES AND THE CLIMATE CHANGE IMPACT (STECCI) PROJECT N°: 101094822**

Project aim
Protection of European cultural heritage from climate change and turning turn the potential of steak necropolises into new opportunities and resources for economic, social and creative entrepreneurship developments of local communities

HORIZON EUROPE · Project Advisor: Melpomeni Vyzika | Diana Leblond-Muresan
STECCI AS WORLD HERITAGE · Sinisa Sesum
STECCI · Project Coordinator Nusret Dreskovic | Saída Ibragic

Event venue
University of Sarajevo
Faculty of Science
Zmaja od Bosne 33-35,
Sarajevo amphitheatre (low building)
09:30 - 10:45

Join us online
Zoom Meeting:
Meeting ID: 829 4175 3798
Funded by the European Union
Passcode: 259306
[Click Here To Join The Zoom Meeting](#)

Consortium

- University of Sarajevo - Coordinator
- Heritage Malta
- Univerzitet Donja Gorica Podgorica
- Universitaet für angewandte Kunst Wien
- Stiftung Preussischer Kulturbesitz
- Zentrum für soziale Innovation GmbH Wien
- Sveučilište u Splitu, Umjetnicka akademija
- Faculty of Sciences University of Novi Sad
- Institut Mines-Telecom

The bottom right corner features the Horizon Europe logo and the European Union logo with the text 'Funded by the European Union'.

EVENT AGENDA TEMPLATE

The event agenda template was created in Microsoft Word. On the top page, there is an A4 format with a grey background, a colored European Commission logo, and the original STECCI LOGO. The agenda text should be written in white lettering, Helvetica typeface, 11pt.

The image shows a grey background with a white text box at the top left containing the European Union logo and the text "Funded by the European Union". In the center, the word "AGENDA" is written in white. Below it, the following text is centered: "Kick-off meeting", "Stone monument ensembles and the climate change impact", "STEC CI", "ID: 101094822HORIZON-CL2-2022-HERITAGE-01", "Type: Hybrid meeting", "September 21 – 23, 2023", and "Sarajevo". Below this is the STECCI logo, which features a stylized golden triangle with a circle on top and the word "STEC CI" in a golden serif font. Underneath the logo, the text "Chairpersons:" is centered. Below that, a list of agenda items is provided in white text: "10:30-10:35 Agenda approval, proposed by Chair (voting)", "10:35-10:40 STECCI project (Overview, objectives, outcomes)", "10:40-10:45 UNSA ppt presentation, including brief overview of role within the STECCI", "10:45-10:50 HM ppt presentation, including brief overview of role within the STECCI", and "10:50-10:55 UDG ppt presentation, including brief overview of role within the STECCI". At the bottom of the page, a small white text box contains the message: "Please reconsider not printing out this document, because we want to preserve nature too."

Funded by
the European Union

AGENDA

Kick-off meeting
Stone monument ensembles and the climate change impact
STEC CI
ID: 101094822HORIZON-CL2-2022-HERITAGE-01
Type: Hybrid meeting
September 21 – 23, 2023
Sarajevo

Chairpersons:

10:30-10:35 Agenda approval, proposed by Chair (voting)
10:35-10:40 STECCI project (Overview, objectives, outcomes)
10:40-10:45 UNSA ppt presentation, including brief overview of role within the
STEC CI 10:45-10:50 HM ppt presentation, including brief overview of role within the
STEC CI 10:50-10:55 UDG ppt presentation, including brief overview of role within
the STECCI

Please reconsider not printing out this document, because we want to preserve nature too.

MEETING MINUTES TEMPLATE

The meeting minutes template was created in Microsoft Word. On the top page, there is an A4 format with a grey background, a coloured European Commission logo, and the original STECCI LOGO. The agenda text should be written in white lettering, Helvetica typeface, 11pt.

The image shows a meeting minutes template on a grey background. At the top left is the European Union logo with the text "Funded by the European Union". In the center, the title "Stone monument ensembles and the climate change impact - STECCI" is displayed, along with the ID "ID: 101094822 HORIZON-CL2-2022-HERITAGE-01". Below this is the STECCI logo, which features a stylized Greek letter Delta (Δ) and the acronym STECCI. The template includes several fields for meeting details: "Minutes from", "Stone monument ensembles and the climate change impact", "Date:", "Place:", "Meeting type:", "Chairperson:", "Present in-person:", and "Present online:". A horizontal line is drawn under the "Present online:" field. At the bottom, a note states: "Minutes are presented during the meeting and adopted by all participants." and a footer message reads: "Please reconsider not printing out this document, because we want to preserve nature too."

Funded by
the European Union

Stone monument ensembles and the climate change impact - STECCI
ID: 101094822 HORIZON-CL2-2022-HERITAGE-01

Minutes from
Stone monument ensembles and the climate change impact
Date:
Place:
Meeting type:
Chairperson:
Present in-person:
Present online:

Minutes are presented during the meeting and adopted by all participants.

Please reconsider not printing out this document, because we want to preserve nature too.

EVENT LIST OF ATTENDEES TEMPLATE

The attendees list for the event was created within Microsoft Word document. A4 in size, including a white background, the original STECCI logo, and a coloured logo of the European Commission on the front page. The information of the agenda has to be given in 11 point Helvetica font with black lettering.

LIST OF ATTENDEES				
Horizon Europe Project No: 101094822				
Stone monument ensembles and the climate change impact				
STECI				
Event:				
Venue:				
Date:				
Organisers:				
1.	Name	Organization	E-mail	Signature
2.				
3.				
4.				
5.				
6.				
Horizon Europe Project No: 101094822				
Stone monument ensembles and the climate change impact - STECI				

POWER-POINT PRESENTATION TEMPLATE

The PowerPoint presentation template was created using the official Microsoft PowerPoint application. The template makes multiple alternatives for the cover page of the presentation, agenda slides, slides containing general content, title slides, mind map diagrams, chart designs, timeline slides, and slides containing aims and objectives.

Heading 1

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Duis vulputate nulla at ante rhoncus, vel efficitur felis condimentum. Proin odio odio.

STONE MONUMENT ENSEMBLES AND THE CLIMATE CHANGE IMPACT

Heading 1

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Duis vulputate nulla at ante rhoncus, vel efficitur felis condimentum. Proin odio odio.

Timeline

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Duis vulputate nulla at ante rhoncus, vel efficitur felis condimentum. Proin odio odio.

1st Quarter
List a milestone or deadline.

2nd Quarter
List a milestone or deadline.

3rd Quarter
List a milestone or deadline.

4th Quarter
List a milestone or deadline.

STONE MONUMENT ENSEMBLES AND THE CLIMATE CHANGE IMPACT

Timeline

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Duis vulputate nulla at ante rhoncus, vel efficitur felis condimentum. Proin odio odio.

1st Quarter
List a milestone or deadline.

2nd Quarter
List a milestone or deadline.

3rd Quarter
List a milestone or deadline.

4th Quarter
List a milestone or deadline.

01

JANUARY

02

FEBRUARY

03

MARCH

04

APRIL

STONE MONUMENT ENSEMBLES AND THE CLIMATE CHANGE IMPACT

GOALS AND OBJECTIVES

Objective n° 1
Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Duis vulputate nulla at ante rhoncus, vel efficitur felis condimentum. Proin odio odio.

Objective n° 2
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Objective n° 3
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STONE MONUMENT ENSEMBLES AND THE CLIMATE CHANGE IMPACT

GOALS AND OBJECTIVES

Objective n° 1
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Objective n° 2
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Objective n° 3
Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Duis vulputate nulla at ante rhoncus, vel efficitur felis condimentum. Proin odio odio.

TARGET AUDIENCE

Target Audience #1

Target Audience #2

Target Audience #3

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Duis vulputate nulla at ante rhoncus, vel efficitur felis condimentum. Proin odio odio.

STONE MONUMENT ENSEMBLES AND THE CLIMATE CHANGE IMPACT

TARGET AUDIENCE

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Duis vulputate nulla at ante rhoncus, vel efficitur felis condimentum. Proin odio odio.

Target Audience #1

Target Audience #2

Target Audience #3

PERIODICAL REPORT TEMPLATE

A template for a periodic report was created in Microsoft Word on an A4 page with a white background, a large STECCI logo on a blue background, and the EU logo on the front page. The designation of the project ought to be typeset in Helvetica 14 in the color blue. The title of the report should be presented in Helvetica 20 font, using the color blue. The recommended font for body text is Helvetica 12 with black letters.

REPORT ON WP X TASK X. Y

Project acronym: STECCI

Project full title: STone monument Ensembles and the Climate Change Impact

Programme: European Commission, Horizon Europe

Project ID: 101094822

Delivery date: 11/2023

Deliverable type: Periodic report

Dissemination level: SEN

Leader

Authors:

DISCLAIMER

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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HISTORY OF CHANGES

Version	Issue date
1.0	October 31 st , 2023

No.	Participant organisation name	Steering committee	Country	Organisation Type
1	Univerzitet u Sarajevu	Nusret Dreskovic (coordinator) Saida Ibragic (project manager)	B&H	University
2	Heritage Malta	Anthony Cassar	MT	National Agency
3	Univerzitet Donja Gorica Podgorica	Andjela Jaksic-Stojanovic	MNE	University
4	Universität für angewandte Kunst Wien	Gabriela Krist	AT	University
5	Stiftung Preussischer Kulturbesitz	Stefan Simon	DE	Cultural Heritage Foundation
6	Zentrum für soziale Innovation GmbH Wien	Pamela Bartar	AT	Institute
7	Sveuciliste u Splitu, Umjetnicka akademija	Siniša Bizjak	HR	University
8	University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences	Snezana Radulovic	SRB	University
9	Institut Mines-Telecom	Vincent Thiery	FR	University

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1.
1.1
1.8.1

SIMPLE REPORT – COLOUR TEMPLATE

A simple report template was created in Microsoft Word on an A4 page with a white background, a large STECCI logo on a blue background, and the EU logo on the front page. The designation of the project ought to be typeset in Helvetica 11 in the color blue. The title of the report ought to be presented in Helvetica 11 font, in the color black. Additionally, a content disclaimer is shown in blue color and DM Sans (Body) font size 9pt. The recommended font for body text is Helvetica 12 with black letters.

STONE MONUMENT ENSEMBLES AND THE CLIMATE CHANGE IMPACT

PROJECT ID: 101098422

TITLE:

Lorem Ipsum is simply dummy text of the printing and typesetting industry. Lorem Ipsum has been the industry's standard dummy text ever since the 1500s, when an unknown printer took a galley of type and scrambled it to make a type specimen book.

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SIMPLE BLACK WHITE REPORT TEMPLATE

A simple report template was created in Microsoft Word on an A4 page with a white background, a large STECCI logo on a blue background, and the EU logo on the front page. The designation of the project need to be typeset in Helvetica 11 in the color black. The title of the report should be given in Helvetica 11 font, in the color black. The recommended font for body text is Helvetica 12 with black letters.

**Funded by
the European Union**

gravida quis blandit. Imperdiet sed euismod nisi porta lorem. Tristique et egestas quis ipsum suspendisse ultrices gravida dictum fusce. Adipiscing elit ut aliquam purus sit amet luctus venenatis lectus. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet consectetur adipiscing. Et pharetra pharetra massa massa ultricies. Euismod lacinia at quis risus.

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DELIVERABLE TEMPLATE

The deliverable template was created in Microsoft Word on an A4 page with a white backdrop, a huge STECCI logo on a blue background, and the EU logo on the front page. The title of the project ought to be typeset in Helvetica 14 in blue. The title of the report should be presented in Helvetica 20 font, using blue. The recommended font for body text is Helvetica 12 with black letters.

STECCI

DELIVERABLE 1.1 – PROJECT MANAGEMENT PLAN

Project acronym: STECCI
Project full title: STone monument Ensembles and the Climate Change Impact
Programme: European Commission, Horizon Europe
Project ID: 101094822
Delivery date: 11/2023
Deliverable type R
Dissemination level
Leader
Authors:

HISTORY OF CHANGES

Version	Issue date
1.0	October 31 th , 2023

STECCI

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STECCI

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1.

1.1

1.2

STECCI

Table 1.

No.	Participant organisation name	Steering committee	Country	Organisation Type
1	Univerzitet u Sarajevu	Nusret Dreskovic (coordinator) Saida Ibragic (project manager)	B&H	University
2	Heritage Malta	Anthony Cassar	MT	National Agency
3	Univerzitet Donja Gorica Podgorica	Andjela Jaksic-Stojanovic	MNE	University
4	Universität für angewandte Kunst Wien	Gabriela Krist	AT	University
5	Stiftung Preussischer Kulturbesitz	Stefan Simon	DE	Cultural Heritage Foundation
6	Zentrum für soziale Innovation GmbH Wien	Pamela Bartar	AT	Institute
7	Sveučiliste u Splitu, Umjetnicka akademija	Siniša Bizjak	HR	University
8	University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences	Snezana Radulovic	SRB	University
9	Institut Mines-Telecom	Vincent Thiery	FR	University

1.3

1.4

Table 2.

1.7

Figure X. Y

2.

2.1

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GENERAL BRAND GUIDELINE

Brand guideline contains general recommendations about the project official correspondence and materials design.

The logotype is the main version to be used in all materials

Symbol with STECCI acronym for social media

STEECI

PRIMARY COLOUR CONFIGURATION

Hex #161DAE

SECONDARY COLOUR CONFIGURATION

Hex #3D3D3D

Black and White CONFIGURATION

RECOMMENDED CLEAR SPACE

TYPOGRAPHY

HELVETICA 20 for TITLES,
HELVETICA 11 for text, single space

NOT RECOMMENDED

30 mm

RECOMMENDED SIZE

RECOMMENDED ORNAMENT

COVER PAGE WATERMARK

STECCI ROLL UP BANNER

STECCI roll up banner was designed in the Adobe Photoshop software. It was designed on the canvas size 200x84cm. White background with the STECCI watermark overlay, white STECCI logo, coloured European commission logo, title and QR code of the project, list and the map of the project consortium.

APPENDIX 5. EMDESK EXCHANGE INTERNAL PLATFORM

PHASE 1 – COMMUNICATION AND CONVDERSATION

Development of the Workplan structure

The EMDESK workplan acts as a tool for project planning, monitoring, and execution, enabling the creation of a project time plan (work breakdown structure) as well as the management and execution of scheduled activities and events (e.g. deliverables, milestones). A hierarchy can be delineated to represent these activities and events. An activity has the capacity to be decomposed into any structure that is preferred, such as a work package, project, tasks, or subtasks. Access management is integrated with the Workplan, allowing participants to be granted varying levels of privileges relative to users or groups for the entire area, or to have access to certain activities and events customized.

Various views Table, Kanban, and Gantt can be used to manage the workplan. They provide an overview of the scheduled work and its progress, as well as the preferred manner of working for each team user .It is possible to create or access scheduled activities or events from any view.

Table View

The Table view is a collapsible spreadsheet containing a list of all activities and events associated with the hierarchical project plan. A list of all events, actions, and their attributes is shown in columns and rows. By adding or removing columns and applying table header filters, the Table view can be modified.

Kanban View

The Kanban view is a graphical workflow management tool utilized to track the completion of tasks and activities. Activities or events are visually depicted with cards that are arranged in columns on a board according to their status.

Gantt View

A graphical timetable, the Gantt chart emphasizes the visualization and scheduling of events and activities, as well as their interdependencies. It is a straightforward application for visualizing the Work Breakdown Structure (WBS), the overall project's and each item's schedule, item dependencies, and item status.

ID	Name	Assignees	Lead Participant	Start	End	Actual Start	Actual End
66	WP 1 Project mana...		UNSA	M01	M48	01.09.23 (M01)	31.08.27 (M48)
70	WP 2 Risk and vul...		UNSA	M02	M40	-	-
71	WP 3 Condition es...		UAA	M01	M44	-	-
72	WP 4 Digitisation		HM	M04	M39	-	-
73	WP 5 Community...		ZSI	M02	M43	-	-

ID	Name	Assignees	Lead Participant	Start	End	Actual Start	Actual End
72	WP 4 Digitisation		HM	M04	M39	-	-
73	WP 5 Community...		ZSI	M02	M43	-	-
74	WP 6 Economic va...		UDG	M04	M36	-	-
75	WP 7 Disseminati...		UNSPMF	M01	M48	-	-
76	WP 8 Ethics requir...		UNSA	M01	M48	-	-

ID	Name	Assignees	Lead Participant	Start	End	Actual Start	Actual End
66	WP 1 Project mana...		UNSA	M01	M48	01.09.23 (M01)	31.08.27 (M48)
70	WP 2 Risk and vul...		UNSA	M02	M40	-	-
71	WP 3 Condition es...		UAA	M01	M44	-	-
72	WP 4 Digitisation		HM	M04	M39	-	-
73	WP 5 Community...		ZSI	M02	M43	-	-

New features!
 Whats new?
 Introducing Timesheets! Now you can track and log your project hours with our new advanced timesheet functionality.
[Learn more](#)

The screenshot shows the STECCI EMDESK interface with a table view of work packages. The table has columns for ID, Name, Assignees, Lead Participant, Start, End, Actual Start, and Actual End. The data is as follows:

ID	Name	Assignees	Lead Participant	Start	End	Actual Start	Actual End
72	WP 4 Digitisation	[User]	HM	M04	M39	-	-
73	WP 5 Community...	[User]	ZSI	M02	M43	-	-
74	WP 6 Economic va...	AJ	UDG	M04	M36	-	-
75	WP 7 Disseminatio...	[User]	UNSPMP	M01	M48	-	-
76	WP 8 Ethics requir...	[User]	UNSA	M01	M48	-	-
93 items				M01	M48	-	-

This screenshot shows the details for WP 3, titled "WP 3 Condition assessment, monitoring and...". The interface includes a sidebar with navigation options and a main content area with the following details:

- ID:** WP 3
- Description:** Activity description
- Objectives:** The primary goal of WP3 is to provide the base for long term preservation strategies of different cultural assets made of compact limestone within the current context of exposure and taking into account the changing climatic conditions (WP2) in eight different regions in Europe. The single steps of the process are as follows:
 - Through condition assessment, decay analyses and the monitoring

This screenshot shows the details for WP 4, titled "WP 4 Digitisation". The interface includes a sidebar with navigation options and a main content area with the following details:

- ID:** WP 4
- Description:** Description of work. The following objectives will be met in a timely manner and will be delivered by experienced staff who have worked on various digitisation projects and who are fully committed to the project. Their main responsibilities cover:
 - the digital acquisition using different low cost acquisition methods (Photogrammetry), laser scanning) of cultural heritage assets found on site as well as overall site documentation
 - Post processing of acquired data to produce 3D models of the digitised assets - including 3D models of the sites as well as 3D models of individual artefacts. A combination of Lidar and Photogrammetry will be used.
- Objectives:** The objective of WP4 is to manage and coordinate the digitization

The screenshot shows the STECCI EMDESK interface. On the left is a navigation sidebar with options like Dashboard, Workplan, Participants, Resources, Analytics, Documents, Contacts, Meetings, Groups, and Users. The main area is split into two panes. The left pane shows a 'Table' view of the workplan with columns for ID, Name, Assignees, and Lead. The right pane shows a detailed view for 'WP 5 Community-based impact strategies', including fields for ID, Description, and Objectives.

ID	Name	Assignees	Lead
72	WP 4	AP	
73	WP 5		
111	Task 5.1		
112	Task 5.2		
113	Task 5.3		

WP 5 Community-based impact strategies
 ID: WP 5
 Description: Activity description
 Objectives: Today, the stecci mediaeval tombstone graveyards are a symbol of cooperation and peacekeeping and have the potential to support wellbeing and inclusive growth in the region due to their intercultural nature. Considering this potential, the WP aims to embed tangible cultural heritage in local and regional ecosystems. This is done with the help of local stakeholders and a people-centred approach putting their needs into the centre of endeavours by asking how the local community can benefit from cultural heritage? 1. Co-Creation of a community-based research strategy -

The screenshot shows the STECCI EMDESK interface. The left pane shows a 'Table' view of the workplan. The right pane shows a detailed view for 'WP 6 Economic values', including fields for ID, Description, and Objectives.

ID	Name	Assignees	Lead
112	D 5.4		
74	WP 6		
115	Task 6.1		
116	Task 6.2		
117	Task 6.3		

WP 6 Economic values
 ID: WP 6
 Description: Activity description
 Objectives: The main objectives are: • to assess the economic impact of climate change on tombstone heritage under different climate scenarios; • to undertake a comprehensive and in-depth analysis of the economic benefits associated with reducing climate change damages to tombstone heritage; • to address economic benefits associated with the preservation of tombstone heritage; • to predict future benefits of

The screenshot shows the STECCI EMDESK interface. The left pane shows a 'Table' view of the workplan. The right pane shows a detailed view for 'WP 7 Dissemination, exploitation and communication', including fields for ID, Description, and Objectives.

ID	Name	Assignees	Lead
113	D 6.1		
153	M 10		
144	D 6.2		
75	WP 7		
119	Task 7.1		

WP 7 Dissemination, exploitation and communication
 ID: WP 7
 Description: Activity description
 Objectives: The main goals of the STECCI project dissemination is transferring the academic excellence to the wider academic and non-academic social network and open public developed networks, following the matrix of Science to Society. The STECCI project advanced interdisciplinary (climatology, ecology, chemistry, conservation, archaeology, cultural heritage, economy, tourism and social sciences)

The screenshot shows the STECCI EMDESK interface. On the left is a navigation sidebar with options like Dashboard, Workplan, Participants, Resources, Analytics, Documents, Contacts, Meetings, Groups, and Users. The main workspace is divided into a table view and a detail view. The table view shows a list of tasks:

ID	Name	Assignees
119	Task 7.1	7.1 Developing dis...
121	Task 7.2	7.2 Setting and up...
122	Task 7.3	7.3 Project branding
123	Task 7.4	7.4 Media commu...
124	Task 7.5	7.5 Development, ...

The detail view for Task 7.2 is titled "7.2 Setting and updating of STECCI". It includes fields for Objectives, Predecessors, Lead Participant (PB - UNSPWR), Further Participants (8 selected), Activity Type (WP 7 (Dissemination, exploitation and communication)), Plan Start Date (MO2), and Duration (47 months). A "Save Activity" button is at the bottom right.

This screenshot shows the STECCI EMDESK interface with Task 7.5 selected. The table view shows tasks from ID 122 to 126:

ID	Name	Assignees
122	Task 7.3	7.3 Pro...
123	Task 7.4	7.4 Me...
124	Task 7.5	7.5 Development, ...
125	Task 7.6	7.6 Scientific cont...
126	Task 7.7	7.7 Open Science ...

The detail view for Task 7.5 is titled "7.5 Development, promotion and logistics". The description reads: "Integrating the STECCI community, students, agencies, and stakeholders via project online Platform will strengthen institutional cooperation and the online global visibility of the project results. It will be developed using the programmed keywords search engine database, comprising all the STECCI related material, in an interactive mode, administered by at least P1 and P6 partners, with remote access to the specific topics available without registration. The platform will have a dedicated section for project outputs aimed at stakeholders but it will be open to the wide society, unlimbity. The platform will have two main focus points: a) Milestones and Social". The "Save Activity" button is visible at the bottom right.

This screenshot shows the STECCI EMDESK interface with Task 7.4 selected. The table view shows tasks from ID 119 to 124:

ID	Name	Assignees
119	Task 7.1	7.1 Developing dis...
121	Task 7.2	7.2 Setting and up...
122	Task 7.3	7.3 Project branding
123	Task 7.4	7.4 Media commu...
124	Task 7.5	7.5 Development, ...

The detail view for Task 7.4 is titled "7.4 Media communication and press". The description reads: "WP UNSPWR will create a promotional video for the project. Another video that will include project results near the end of the project (M46). The communication and press activities will be utilized to raise awareness on the project and generate a wider interest for its activities, deliverables. The task leader will maintain the project promotional material in collaboration with the project partners and WP1 leader, as well as the digitized assets will be made available on the project website." A list of assignees is shown, including Snežana Nena Radulović, Sandra I., Amira Sivic, Boka Web Developer, Fran I. Irelja, Biljana Bećanin, Miroslav Vujčić, and Anthony Cassar. The "Save Activity" button is at the bottom right.

The screenshot shows the STECCI Workplan interface. On the left is a navigation sidebar with options like Dashboard, Workplan, Participants, Resources, Documents, Contacts, Meetings, Groups, and Users. The main workspace displays a table of tasks in 'Table' view. A right-hand pane shows the details for 'Task 7.5 Development, promotion and logistics'. A search dropdown is open, listing several participants.

ID	Name	Assignees
119	Task 7.1	7.1 Developing dis...
121	Task 7.2	7.2 Setting and up...
122	Task 7.3	7.3 Project branding
123	Task 7.4	7.4 Media commu...
124	Task 7.5	7.5 Development, ...

Search results for Task 7.5 assignees:

- Anthony Cassar
- Marija Mitcin
- Pamela Marjen Barar
- Stefan Simon
- Ardela Jekić Stojanović
- Siřiša Blizak
- Rexhina Merkuhiuji
- Andrew Pace

The screenshot shows the STECCI Workplan interface. The main workspace displays a table of deliverables (D) and work packages (WP). A right-hand pane shows the details for 'WP 8 Ethics requirements'.

ID	Name	Assignees
149	D 7.5	D 7.5 Policy sheet 1
150	D 7.6	D 7.6 S1E-C33 inter...
151	D 7.7	D 7.7 Disseminatio...
152	D 7.8	D 7.8 Policy sheet 2
76	WP 8	WP 8 Ethics requir...

Details for WP 8:

- ID:** WP 8
- Description:** This work package sets out the 'ethics requirements' that the project must comply with.
- Objectives:** The objective is to ensure compliance with the 'ethics requirements' set out in this work package.
- Predecessors:** Select Predecessors
- Lead Participant:** P1 COO - UNISA

CREATING, EDITING, AND ORGANIZING PARTICIPANTS

The following attributes were configured for the new participant:

- Logo
- Name
- ID
- Short/Code
- Description Participant card

EMDESK Users and Groups setup

Each user is assigned a specific access level or role and a specified set of access rights per workspace. These rights control the functionalities and modifications that a user is permitted to do within the workspace. There are four different access levels / roles with a defined set of access rights:

- **Owner:** The designated legal contact to EMDESK, the project and subscription owner is responsible for invoices and payments. By default, the owner is the person who created the project. There is only one owner for each project. The owner is marked by a crown in the "Users" section. The owner is the only user who can delete the project.
- **Admin:** Has full access to the project and is responsible for the technical administration of the project. Can be more than one.
- **Manager:** Has almost full access to the project, but no access to "Subscription". Can be more than one.
- **Regular User:** Any user who is not the *Owner*, *Admin*, or *Manager*. Has restricted read access to technical settings and general project information. To determine what the user can read, edit, and manage, the defined access rights must be set. Can be more than one.

ACCESS RIGHTS OF REGULAR USERS

The following access rights options are available per each section and item:

- **Manage:** The user has full access to the data – can see, edit, and manage (add, move, or delete) workspace items.
- **Edit:** The user can see and edit workspace items, but cannot manage them (add, move, or delete).
- **Read:** The user can see workspace items, add comments and attachments, but cannot edit and manage items (add, move, or delete).
- **Off:** The user has no access to workspace items.

Users / Groups	Access Level		Access Rights			
	Admin	Manager	Activities	Participants	Documents	Resources
Marija Michin Universität für angewandte Kunst Wien	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> / Refine	<input type="checkbox"/> / Refine	<input type="checkbox"/> / Refine	Manage
Pamela Marjan Barter ZSL - Project Manager	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> / Refine	<input type="checkbox"/> / Refine	<input type="checkbox"/> / Refine	Manage
Stefan Simon Erlangen-Forschungslabor Staatliche Museen zu Berlin - Director	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> / Refine	<input type="checkbox"/> / Refine	<input type="checkbox"/> / Refine	Manage
Andeja Jakšić Stojanović University of Donja Gorica - dean of Faculty of culture and tourism	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> / Refine	<input type="checkbox"/> / Refine	<input type="checkbox"/> / Refine	Manage
Siniša Bizjak dielarnik	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> / Refine	<input type="checkbox"/> / Refine	<input type="checkbox"/> / Refine	Manage

D7.1 Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan

Users / Group	Access Level	Access Rights
UNISA - Full Professor	Admin	Activities, Participants, Documents, Resources
Anthony Cassar Heritage Malta - Head		Refine, Refine, Refine, Manage
Marja Michin Universität für angewandte Kunst Wien		Refine, Refine, Refine, Manage
Pamela Marjan Barar ZKS - Project Manager		Refine, Refine, Refine, Manage
Stefan Simon Institut für architekturlabor Staatliche Museen zu Berlin - Director		Refine, Refine, Refine, Manage
Andea Jakšić-Štorgajević University of Donja Gorica - dean of Faculty of culture and tourism		Refine, Refine, Refine, Manage

Group name	Member	Group Manager	Group Email Address	Access Level
1. WP1 UNISA Project Management	3 Member (1 Requests)	Nusret Drešković UNISA - Full Professor	stecowp1@groups.emdesk.com	Restricted
2. WP2 UNISA Risk and vulnerability assessment based on climate scenarios	10 Member	Nusret Drešković UNISA - Full Professor	-	Open
3. WP3 Condition assessment	5 Member	Edin Hrejša University of Sarajevo - Faculty of Science - Assistant Professor	-	Open
4. WP4 Digitalisation	10 Member	Edin Hrejša University of Sarajevo - Faculty of Science - Assistant Professor	-	Open

Group name	Member	Group Manager	Group Email Address	Access Level
1. WP1 UNISA Project Management	3 Member (1 Requests)	Nusret Drešković UNISA - Full Professor	stecowp1@groups.emdesk.com	Restricted
2. WP2 UNISA Risk and vulnerability assessment based on climate scenarios	10 Member	Nusret Drešković UNISA - Full Professor	-	Open
3. WP3 Condition assessment	5 Member	Edin Hrejša University of Sarajevo - Faculty of Science - Assistant Professor	-	Open
4. WP4 Digitalisation	10 Member	Edin Hrejša University of Sarajevo - Faculty of Science - Assistant Professor	-	Open

Group name	Member	Group Manager	Group Email Address	Access Level
6. WP6 Economic values	7 Member	Edin Hrejša University of Sarajevo - Faculty of Science - Assistant Professor	-	Open
7. WP7 DEC	29 Member	Snježana Nena Radulović UNISPMF - Full Professor	-	Open
8. WP8 Ethics	5 Member	Saida I UNISA PMP	-	Open
Partner representative	11 Member	Saida I UNISA PMP	-	Open
UNISPMF	13 Member	Snježana Nena Radulović UNISPMF - Full Professor	unispmp@groups.emdesk.com	Open

Users of an account were categorized into groups. By joining or leaving the group the users can automatically gain or lose the access rights set for the group.

Guests

The screenshot shows the 'Guests' management page in the EMDESK system. The interface includes a search bar, a table of guest profiles, and columns for access rights across different categories: Activities, Participants, Documents, and Resources. Each guest profile includes a name, photo, and affiliation.

Guests	Activities	Participants	Documents	Resources
AS Amira Sivic Faculty of Science, University of Sarajevo - Assistant Professor	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read
KB Boka Web Developer Stecci	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Off
BS Bilana Besarin UNSP/IF	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read
UV Miroslav Vujicic UNSP/IF - Associate Professor	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read
MR Reshina Merihotaj 750 - Research Assistant	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read
AP Andrew Pace Heritage Malta	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read

This screenshot displays another set of guest profiles in the EMDESK system. The layout is consistent with the previous screenshot, showing a search bar, a list of guests, and columns for access rights to Activities, Participants, Documents, and Resources.

Guests	Activities	Participants	Documents	Resources
KB Krasimira Bogdan EMMS - Senior Engineer	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read
UV Gordana Vukobratovic UNSP/IF - Head of International Relations Office	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read
MM Mirna Mujcinic EMMS - General secretary	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read
TM Tiney Melina Saban Heritage Malta - Coordinator	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read
SC Sae Ekan Perang Gregory Heritage Malta - Finance Manager	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read
LC Ljiljana Corina Heritage Malta - Finance Director	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read

This screenshot shows a third set of guest profiles in the EMDESK system. It features a search bar, a list of guests, and columns for access rights to Activities, Participants, Documents, and Resources.

Guests	Activities	Participants	Documents	Resources
UN UNSA - Assistant	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read
SD Samir Dug Profesor matematički fakultet Sarajevo - Professor	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read
R Renata.bge@unsa.ba	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read
DP Drososlav Pavic University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences - Professor	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read
MM Miroslav Mesaros University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences - Associate Professor	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read
BR Branka Radulovic University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences - Associate Professor	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read

This screenshot displays a fourth set of guest profiles in the EMDESK system. The interface includes a search bar, a list of guests, and columns for access rights to Activities, Participants, Documents, and Resources.

Guests	Activities	Participants	Documents	Resources
MA Maja Perokovic Faculty of Science, University of Novi Sad - Teaching assistant	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read
JA Jasmina Agic University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences - Lecturer	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read
ZP Zorica Podreacanin University of Novi Sad	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read
US Ugljesa Stankev UNSP/IF, UN/IF - Full professor	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read
GA Goran Anackovic University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Department Ecology and Ecology - Full professor	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read / Refine	Read

5. Document Manager

All the Documents can be accessed in Document EMDESK space

D7.1 Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan

EMDESK Meetings

STECCI | Help | 31 | EMDESK

Version V1 | Active Plan | Reporting ON

All

ID	Subject	Date	Time	Attendees	Meeting Link	Status
19	EMDESK Meeting	26.06.21	17:00	[User Avatars]	-	Expired
20	STECI WPS meet...	04.12.23	14:00	[User Avatars]	-	Expired
21	EMDESK Meeting	06.11.23	14:20	[User Avatars]	-	Expired
22	Reporting	14.11.23	14:00	[User Avatars]	-	Expired
23	EMDESK Meeting	29.11.23	11:00	[User Avatars]	-	Expired
24	UDG and UNSPMF ...	22.11.23	13:30	[User Avatars]	-	Expired

Start Meeting

STECCI | Help | 31 | EMDESK

Version V1 | Active Plan | Reporting ON

All

ID	Subject	Date	Time	Attendees	Meeting Link	Status
25	STECI WP4 meeting	20.12.23	10:00	[User Avatars]	https://stecci-emdesk.com/...	Upcoming

Start Meeting

Workflow / Activities

STECCI | Help | Restart tutorial | 31 | EMDESK

Version V1 | Active Plan | Reporting ON

Dashboard - Activity Stream

3 hours ago (10:18)	Siniša Bijač Siniša Bijač changed Participant 'P7 - UMAS'	Phone was changed from '+385915406104' to ''
4 hours ago (10:09)	Siniša Bijač Siniša Bijač changed Participant 'P7 - UMAS'	City was set to 'Split' Address 1 was set to 'Zagrebačka 3' Post code was set to '21000' Phone was set to '+385915406104' Website was set to 'https://www.umass.unist.hr/'
4 hours ago (10:08)	Siniša Bijač Siniša Bijač changed Participant 'P7 - UMAS'	Description was updated
4 hours ago (09:33)	You changed Participant 'PB - UNSPMF'	HideRates was set to On
Yesterday 18:24	Edin Hreija changed Folder 'Deliverables - WP1' at Folder 'Home'	Location was changed from 'Activities WPS' to 'Home'

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Dashboard - Notifications

Cockpit | Activity Stream | Notifications

Mark all as read | Email Settings

Today	3 hours ago (10:20)	Participant 'PB - UNSPMF'	Modified
	4 hours ago (10:18)	Participant 'P7 - UMAS'	Modified
Yesterday	Yesterday 18:24	Folder 'Deliverables - WP1'	Modified
	Yesterday 18:15	Meeting 'STECI Financial/Admin Issues II Meeting 'STECI Financial/Admin Issues II' is running by Nina Begović.	Join
	Yesterday 16:10	Participant 'P4 - UAA'	Modified
	Yesterday 12:59	Participant 'P2 - HM'	Modified
	Yesterday 11:23	Expense '#58 E119.48 C.3 Other goods, works and services for P4 - UAA' at Activity 'Task 2.1'	Modified
	Yesterday 11:13	Expense '#57 4763.14 C.1 Tands for P4 - UAA' at Activity 'Task 1.3'	Modified
	Yesterday 08:45	Document 'STECI WPS MINUTES_041223_ZS' at Folder 'MINUTES meeting 04/12/2023'	Modified

This EMDESK option allows users to make and read comments on project items. Comments appear in a chronological order with the newest at the bottom. In addition, all comments are shown in a chronological order in the "Dashboard" section in the "Cockpit" tab. Commenting is available for the following types of workspace items:

- Activities
- Events
- Participants
- Budget entries
- Expenses records
- EMDocs per section